

Products from Hydrazines: Carbonyl Derivatives of Some α -Benzamido- β -phenylacrylohydrazides

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In continuation of our previous work³, a few substituted α -benzamido- β -phenylacrylohydrazides have been prepared and condensed with a few aliphatic and aromatic carbonyl compounds to obtain acylhydrazones required in connection with some other studies in these laboratories.

α -Benzamido- β -phenyl¹-, β -(3-nitrophenyl)²-, β -(4-methoxyphenyl)-, and β -(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)¹-acrylohydrazides and their hydrazones were prepared by the procedures reported earlier³.

TABLE I
Carbonyl derivatives of hydrazides.

a : $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=R_5=H$.

b : $R_2=NO_2$; $R_1=R_3=R_4=R_5=H$.

c : $R_3=OMe$; $R_1=R_2=R_4=R_5=H$.

d : $R_4=CH_2O_2$; $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$.

	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
1. Benzaldehyde.								
a.	*233-34°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	11.51	11.37	230°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄	13.61	13.52
b.	218°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄	13.68	13.52	255°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₅	15.41	15.24
c.	+215°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.30	10.54	228°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	12.81	12.61
d.	210°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	10.41	10.16	238°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₄	12.43	12.22
3. Anisaldehyde.								
a.	196°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.81	10.62	205°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	10.31	10.16
b.	210°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	12.82	12.61	225°	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₄	12.41	12.22
c.	223°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃	9.91	9.77	217°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	9.62	9.47
d.	231°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	9.21	9.48	228°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃	9.02	9.18
4. Piperonal.								

1. Budovskii *et al.*, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1961, **31**, 1297; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 27275i.

2. Jennings, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1512.

3. Deorha and Gupta, *this Journal*, 1964, **41**, 739.

*Budovskii *et al.*, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1960, **30**, 2569, report m.p. 231°.

†Vangheloveci and Moiso, *Chem. Abs.*, 1944, **38**, 5500, report m.p. 212°.

TABLE I (contd.)

M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
		Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.	
	5. Vanilline.				6. Cinnamaldehyde.			
a.	236°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	10.26	10.11	190°	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃	10.52	10.62
b.	231°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	12.01	12.16	200°	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	12.91	12.71
c.	223°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	9.61	9.43	200°	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	10.12	9.87
d.	220°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₃	9.41	9.14	222°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	9.71	9.56
	7. Salicylaldehyde.				8. Ethyl methyl ketone.			
a.	225°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	11.16	10.90	186°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃	12.62	12.52
b.	232°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₄	13.23	13.01	170°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	14.51	14.73
c.	226°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	10.31	10.11	167°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃	11.71	11.50
d.	251°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₃	9.52	9.78	182°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	11.31	11.07

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